

Artificial intelligence in contemporary higher education: Opportunities and challenges

Georgios Patsiaouras*, Sylvian Jesudoss and John Balabanis

School of Business, University of Leicester, Leicester LE2 1RQ, United Kingdom

*Correspondence: E-mail: gp83@le.ac.uk

Abstract

This paper seeks to elaborate on the opportunities and challenges stemming from the increased use of AI in Higher Education. First, we critically analyse some negative consequences from AI misuse in HE with emphasis on the threats of algorithmic bias, and the rise of educational and digital inequalities. Second, we highlight the opportunities stemming from AI use in HE around the automation of tasks, personalization and accessibility. Finally, we conclude by providing a critical discussion about the future use of AI in universities and Higher Education and we indicate areas for future research and critical considerations of AI applications across different parts of the globe.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence; Higher Education.*

JEL Classification: I21; I23; O33.

1. Introduction

The gradual growth and application of Artificial Intelligence is expected to have a massive and transformative impact on every industry and sector (Harding, 2024). Likewise, Artificial Intelligence (AI henceforth) has already been transforming the process of teaching and learning in Higher Education institutions around the globe (Sollosy & McInerney, 2022).

The arrival of AI does not constitute the first radical wave, wherein technology shaped learning, teaching, and education in general. For example, the invention of the printing press constituted a ground-breaking moment in human history, since the increasing speed of book production democratized access to knowledge and information (McLuhan, 1962). Complex diagrams, mathematical equations, and engineering designs that relied on confusing hand-drawing results could be precisely reproduced and disseminated across the world for the benefit of millions of students (Eisenstein, 1980). Similarly, the Internet provided students from all over the world with similar access to a wide range of online materials, resources, and information. Accordingly, HE providers managed to strengthen students' educational experience through flexible learning opportunities and interactive activities (Ryan et al, 2000; Clegg, Hudson & Steel, 2003). Like all types of technological revolutions, we observe that together with opportunities, threats arise from the adoption of new tools and methods of learning and teaching in HE. Whilst the speed, volume, and quality of shared information and pedagogical material increased exponentially, issues around copyright infringement, digital literacy gaps and the spread of disinformation came to the surface (Webster, 2006). It is expected that AI's ascendancy in the realm of education will induce both positive and threatening developments in the ways we teach, learn, and interact with technology.

To date, a growing body of literatures has been analysing the impact of AI on Higher Education with emphasis on its applications and consequences regarding teaching and learning strategies (Bearman et al, 2024; Ajani et al, 2024). On the one hand, academics from several fields, concur that AI's transformative potential is a positive force of enhanced education quality, increased standards, and customized learning experiences (Saeger et al, 2024; Stoyanova & Angelova, 2024). On the other hand, the introduction of AI in HE programmes has intensified aspects around plagiarism, factual incorrectness, privacy concerns and loss of skills, amongst others (Ivanov, 2023). Considering that AI technology is nowhere near its full potential (Harari, 2024), educators only begin to grasp the parameters of the new landscape stemming from the interrelated evolution between AI and Higher Education with implications for a variety of activities such as content creation, assessment, interactive and immersive learning, personalisation and flexible content delivery. It becomes evident that a critical approach and analysis on the interface of AI and higher education requires the adoption of wide and interdisciplinary lenses considering the psychological, sociological, entrepreneurial, and socio-economic

implications stemming from machines' ability to simulate human learning, problem solving, decision making, autonomy and creativity (Harding, 2024).

Accordingly, the main aim of this commentary paper is threefold. Firstly, it seeks to identify, highlight and critically discuss some negative aspects of the adoption of AI in Higher Education. Secondly, it aims to identify and emphasize the positive contribution of AI technologies to Higher Education. Thirdly, we conclude with a critical discussion about the future use of AI in universities and Higher Education and we indicate areas for future research and critical considerations of AI applications across different parts of the globe.

2. Threats from the use of artificial intelligence in higher education

The utopian discourse on the impact of AI in higher education takes a techno-deterministic approach and has been described as a transformative and revolutionary solution that can democratise higher education and lead to personalised learning to counter the growing standardisation (Karam, 2023). While the initial applications of AI in education and the creative potential of generative AI have provided some value to the argument, the threats, on the other hand, might outweigh the benefits. While the academic literature has established issues like plagiarism (Ivanov, 2023), hallucination of facts (Ivanov & Soliman, 2023), biased hiring practices, and data governance (Filgueiras, 2024), we can also highlight the broader issues that HEIs might encounter in the future.

The use of AI is expected to amplify the "data colonialism" in higher education. Couldry and Meijas (2019) argue that data colonialism is the extraction and exploitation of data from human life, similar to how resources were exploited in historical colonialism. For example, in Higher Education, data colonialism manifests by the concentration of knowledge production, data, and surveillance in the Global North (Zembylas, 2024). The inclusion of AI can exacerbate social discrimination, influence behaviours, and marginalise the Global South (Arora et al., 2023). Considering that it has been recorded that there is a clear digital divide between nations (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2016), AI constitutes a real threat. Data will be concentrated within particular regions and thereupon knowledge will be homogenised, threatening inclusion policies that have occurred for decades. These types of inequality will emerge at a micro level and especially in cases where students will lack access to appropriate technology. Accordingly, academic staff will be asked to generate types of knowledge that worsen inequality and we can already see examples such as the arrival of AI-based courses in universities that disregard the digital inequalities prevalent within these institutions.

We can recognize another threat around the impact of AI on decision making. For example, AI experts suggest a technical solution called "synthetic data" (Arora et al., 2023) to mitigate algorithmic bias. In the future, generative AI systems can create a layer of "synthetic data" on top of an original dataset by learning from it. This could help rebalance the data, but the development of Causal AI (Rawal et al., 2025) will directly influence decision-making processes. Researchers have pointed out that synthetic data may have problems like diversity-washing, circumventing consent, and reinforcement of existing bias (Whitney & Norman, 2024). Combined with Causal AI, this could lead to biased decisions. For instance, in Higher Education Institutions, AI solutions are proposed to reduce administrative tasks and governance, such as automatic grading, streamlining application processing, scheduling, hiring, and data-driven decisions on curriculum planning, student engagement, and resource allocation. However, such techno-deterministic approach to implementing AI may lead to calamitous issues due to erroneous decisions.

If the decisions are made by the AI systems, it beckons the question of agency and authority. Herzfeld (2023) questions whether AI systems will be tools, partners, or surrogates in decision-making. As more and more autonomous systems are being developed, the agency and authority of humans will be redefined. In some cases of Higher Education, due to the marketisation, the relationship between a teacher and student has become a supplier-consumer relationship (Molesworth et al., 2009). With the advent of AI, this relationship might be transformed into a middleman-consumer relationship, where teachers assume the role of curators instead of knowledge producers. This will not only affect the relationships but also the pedagogy in Higher Education. The shift will result in the loss of autonomy and agency for academics.

The other promise that AI-based pedagogy offers is the personalisation of teaching and learning. Universities with the consumerist approach have pushed academics to provide a "personalised" approach. If the education is hyper-personalised and the academics become mere curators of content produced by AI systems, the market might eventually eliminate the humans (middlemen) involved in the process.

Conclusively, threats such as algorithmic bias and academic integrity are very much rooted in the current capabilities of AI usage. Considering the rapid rise of technology, the growing risks of techno-deterministic decision-making,

loss of autonomy, hyper-personalisation and data colonialism can truly reshape Higher Education. Accordingly, the traditional university structure and its fundamental ethos of learning may face an existential threat.

3. Opportunities from the use of artificial intelligence in higher education

The opportunities stemming from the interface of AI integration and Higher Education might overshadow some of the risks which have been raised by several scholars, as mentioned in the previous section. The application of AI has already transformed various aspects of teaching, learning, and administration, providing opportunities to improve - amongst others - quality, personalisation, and accessibility (Saeger et al., 2024; Stoyanova & Angelova, 2024). For example, the *Digital Education Council Global AI Student Survey* (2024) indicates that 86% of university students have already used AI tools to support their studies, with 24% of them engaging with these tools daily. Following the same survey, amongst the AI functions and uses, the most common have been around information search (69%), followed by grammar check (42%) and document summary (32%). Accordingly, we notice that the wide adoption of AI technologies shows the rise of a massive transformation around student learning environments and behaviours. Along with replacing traditional teaching methods, AI technologies are also becoming part of them by helping students to shape academic skills and to manage increased workloads. As Zhai et al. (2021) argue, intelligent tutoring systems, such as Squirrel AI, and platforms like Judge.org, are delivering real-time feedback that strengthens both student performance and engagement. Accordingly, these novel approaches present pedagogical opportunities to infuse AI into teaching and transform both students' learning and research experiences. Moreover, the *Digital Education Council Global AI Student Survey* (2024) showed that that 58% of student respondents feel that they do not have sufficient knowledge of AI, and that 80% feel that universities do not sufficiently integrate AI into their programs. In the same survey, we notice that 72% of student respondents agree that Universities should provide training on the effective use of AI tools (Digital Education Council, 2024). Thereupon, universities begin to realise that they need to include AI not only into curriculum but also within the supporting infrastructures and learning environments. Moving outside teaching spaces, AI can help universities to strengthen employability and enhance AI ethics awareness, digital fluency and critical engagement with new technologies and AI-mediated workplaces (Saeger et al., 2024; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2020).

Furthermore, and following Narayanan and Kapoor (2025), a large number of universities across the globe are adopting governance structures to manage generative AI, via the introduction of AI steering groups, ethics committees, and review boards. For example, the University of Sydney and Imperial College London are heavily investing in the responsible use of AI and the adoption of new pedagogical formats over the last few years (University of Sydney, 2023; Imperial College London, 2024). Likewise, the Wharton School of the University of Pennsylvania launched a specialised AI degree for its business program (Wharton Newsroom, 2025). Additionally, many more Universities adopt simulations based on AI and real-time learning analytics in order to facilitate educators to focus on creativity and thinking (Bearman et al., 2024; Saaida, 2023). Going back to Zhai et al.'s (2021) systematic review, we notice that AI-supported virtual laboratories and gamified learning environments, including Minecraft Edu, increase student learning and satisfaction.

Moreover, a list by Thesify.ai (2024) detailing the generative AI policies of *The Times Top 20 Universities* of 2024 shows that leading universities, such as Harvard, Oxford, and the National University of Singapore, are formalising their approaches to generative AI through new policies around its use and maintenance of academic integrity. We can argue that the ethical implementation of AI can reduce both administrative burden on academics and accordingly, to free time for mentorship and research-led teaching (Ajani et al., 2024; Michel-Villarreal et al., 2023). Also, the potential of AI in enhancing accessibility and inclusivity in education should not be underestimated. Multilingual translation platforms and real-time transcription systems can help students with disabilities as well as students from various cultural and linguistic backgrounds (Stoyanova & Angelova, 2024). For example, text-to-diagram systems for blind learners and affective computing systems can help inclusion and adjust content based on students' needs and personal learning environments (Zhai et al., 2021; Bearman & Ajjawi, 2023). Conclusively, we can suggest that AI presents several opportunities in higher education to personalise learning, foster digital literacy and widen access to diverse forms of knowledge.

4. Discussion

Overall, this commentary piece sought to present a balanced and structured argumentation around the use and misuse of AI in Higher Education. We conclude by stating that the so-called AI Revolution lies still in an embryonic stage, and

any attempts to forecast its course or direction might be misleading. Similar to previous educational revolutions (printing press and the Internet for example), we argue that the early establishment of ethical frameworks, inter-governmental agreements and common legislative tools will proactively mitigate potential threats. At the same time, we should reflect on access to AI capabilities and tools across the globe and whether its 'democratization' will be truly implemented without geographical or cultural bias. The ethical application of AI will most probably enhance learning experiences and increase productivity across student cohorts and staff members (Ajani et al, 2024). A real challenge is whether this process will also promote inclusivity and accessibility, or whether it might generate technologically 'advanced' and technologically 'semi-advanced' cohorts of students across the globe. Thereupon, it is very important to elaborate on the foundations of AI provision, for example, the spread and growth of AI data centres, 5G and 6G networks and digital technologies (Couldry & Mejias, 2019). Their equal distribution and sustainable use will undoubtedly benefit billions of learners, whilst their mismanagement will only accelerate digital gaps and inequalities.

Accordingly, we close this commentary by stating that the future of AI in HE is based on the choices we will make today. An ethical and careful use of AI will become a positive force for good and social change, whilst its unethical use will risk deepening inequalities. Therefore, we argue that AI is not just a technological tool but a mirror of our societal and technological values and we have the responsibility to insulate Higher Education from growing inequalities. HE policymakers, academics and learners should carefully monitor and implement ethical frameworks to ensure that fair, democratic, and accountable AI use will benefit every student, in every corner of the globe.

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Biographical Note: Dr Georgios Patsiaouras is Associate Professor in Marketing at the School of Business, University of Leicester. His research interests include marketing theory, sustainability and how institutional forces have shaped marketing thought and practice. Dr Sylvian Patrick Jesudoss is Lecturer in Marketing at the School of Business, University of Leicester. His research interests encompass critical marketing, consumer culture theory, and the impact of technology on human behaviour and their ethical implications. Dr John Balabanis is Lecturer in Marketing at the School of Business, University of Leicester. His research interests include digital marketing, international marketing, corporate political activities and political marketing.

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